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THE EDUCATIONAL PHILOSOPHY AND THE CAREER MOTIVATION OF THE PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to explore the educational philosophy and the career motivation of pre-service teachers at the Tayabas Western Academy, Candelaria, Quezon. This study utilizes a descriptive-correlational methodology. According to Melegrito and Mendoza (2016), is a concept in research that explains and analyzes information contextually. This also centered on the situations of established relationships, perspectives that were retained, and methods or patterns that were currently developing. The following major findings are: pre-service teachers exemplify progressivism and existentialism as educational philosophies when viewed as a whole. However, when classified according to the educational program, essentialism was the dominant educational philosophy for BEEd, BSEd English, and BSEd Filipino courses; perennialism philosophy for BSEd General Science course; and existentialism philosophy for BSEd Social Studies and BSEd Mathematics courses. Likewise, pre-service teachers are 'motivated' to choose teaching as a profession. Therefore, it is reasonable to assume that the Tayabas Western Academy pre-service teachers have diverse educational philosophies and are willing to embrace their chosen field of work although teaching is not a simple job. The results suggest modifications of a proactive approach to education programs in the 21st century to strengthen the caliber of their graduates.

Keywords: Educational Philosophy, Career Motivation, Pre-service Teachers, Teacher Education Preparation Program

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INTRODUCTION

The initiatives to strengthen the quality of education in the 21st-century classroom rely on the service of teachers who are sufficiently equipped to execute numerous vital responsibilities in a learning environment. These teachers, in terms of education, are those that have practical knowledge, effective teaching methods, and well-developed educational philosophies. According to Orchard et al. (2021), the educational philosophy is the central value and principle that shapes one's classroom practices, and pedagogical approaches, which entails asking and answering concerns regarding the role and purpose of education in society, the role of students and teachers, the function of the curriculum, and the best instructional methods.

There are five (5) educational philosophies presented in the Philosophy chapter (13) in the Sadker and Sadker (1997) foundations text namely: Essentialism, Perennialism, Progressivism, Social Reconstructionism, and Existentialism. These philosophical approaches to teaching are commonly

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implemented in classrooms because it mostly focuses on the students, what educators should teach, and the characteristics of the curriculum.

In connection, considering that one's beliefs directly affect the way one teaches, as one's experiences shape their beliefs, and one's beliefs shape their pedagogical approach, the efforts to determine the pre-service teachers' educational philosophy can help them comprehend and modify their educational practices, aligning them with the right and effective instructional methodologies (Uzunoz, 2015). Additionally, being aware of the philosophy of education guides and offers pre-service teachers who are just starting their careers a sense of identity.

On the other hand, given the significance of teaching as a profession, it is essential to determine why pre-service teachers choose this field. Ponnock et al. (2018) point out that the motivations of pre-service teachers considering a career in education have an impact on their persistence, effectiveness, and hence, their future students' accomplishments. In this connection, motivation is defined as a factor that drives and initiates an individual towards goal-oriented behaviors and their capacity to do the work efficiently. Teachers can inspire their students when they are immersed and motivated by their learning and growth as individuals.

Research Questions

This study aimed primarily to determine the relationship between the educational philosophy and the career motivation of Fourth-year Education students enrolled during the Academic Year 2021-2022. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the mean distribution of the pre-service teachers to the different educational philosophies?
2. What are the manifested philosophies of the following educational programs:
 - 2.1 BEEd;
 - 2.2 BSED Major in English;
 - 2.3 BSED Major in Filipino;
 - 2.4 BSED Major in General Science;
 - 2.5 BSED Major in Mathematics; and
 - 2.6 BSED Major in Social Studies?
3. What is the level of the pre-service teachers' career motivation for choosing teaching as a profession?
4. Are there significant differences in the pre-service teachers' educational philosophies?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the pre-service teachers' educational philosophy and their career motivation?
6. What are the implications that can be derived from the findings of the study?

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Pre-service teachers' philosophical disposition is an evolving and cumulative component of their character. This is influenced by their behavior as well as their tendency to act consistently in the future, based on a set of internal ideals. With its general meaning, dispositions are most frequently referred to as behaviors, beliefs, and attitudes displayed by humans in both verbal and non-verbal aspects (Cummings & Asempapa, 2013). According to Kirwan and Roumell (2015) as society expects teachers to have upstanding moral behavior and attitudes, considering philosophical orientation as the central part of teacher education preparation programs can help to shape the attitudes and values of teacher candidates, transforming them from someone who possesses basic knowledge and skill of an effective educator. In relation, acquiring educational philosophy is becoming more prevalent among in-service and pre-service teachers, and since it is a continuous process as a result of a change in instructional strategies and professional identities, educators should anticipate their philosophy to develop as their teaching career progresses. This may inspire them in being more thought-provoking, and critical thinkers, which is essential for becoming effective teachers who can compare the actual teaching to beliefs and principles that demonstrate what, why, and how to educate (Center for Research on Learning and Teaching, 2017).

Individually, the goal of essentialism is to impart to students the essentials, or primary things, of academic knowledge, using a back-to-basics approach. Essentialists believe that the purpose of education is to equip students with the foundational knowledge and skills necessary to promote citizenship; they argue that teaching this core curriculum systematically and conscientiously is crucial. Moreover, education's mission is to transfer a shared body of information, skills, concepts, and traditions from generation to generation to convert people to actively and productively participate democratically in life. Hence, this philosophical school of thinking emphasizes intellectual training in language, mathematics, physics, and history that can cater to these concepts (Acquah et al., 2017).

Meanwhile, in perennialism, the primary objective of education is to enhance the mind and to train students to utilize it following logical principles. In light of this, the teacher, as a subject matter expert, assumes responsibility for displaying logical and consistent thought processes (Guttek, 2014). Ergun (2018) emphasizes that progressive education is a paradigm that places the student at the center of the learning process. In this approach, the learning environment must be adapted to the learner's developmental requirements. Individual characteristics must be considered while planning the teaching and learning process. Orchard et al. (2021) argue that rather than preparing students for the real world, in this philosophy, education embodies the real world itself for all students. The classroom should be democratically structured, and student-centered processes and approaches should be employed.

In social reconstructionism, Bueno (2019) emphasizes that students are crucial to social change because they are capable of initiating and responding to change, particularly if they are encouraged by a competent adult role model. In this regard, a social reconstructionist would endeavor to structure the classroom in a manner that is classless, nonsexist, and nonracist. Less emphasis would be placed on administration and control and more on community building. As such, conflict resolution and different ways of looking at the world would be encouraged and supported, which would help students understand themselves and search for purpose in life.

Further, existentialism philosophy is associated with a man's education that makes him a complete human being in his natural environment. In this setting, freedom is integral to a man becoming his full potential. Freedom is given to men so that they can learn about and develop their own identities (Suwarno, 2020). On the other hand, teachers' motivation is considered one of the most essential aspects of students' overall success; however, keeping teachers motivated can be difficult at times. In a general perspective, teachers go into teaching because they aspire to enhance the lives of children. On top of that, teachers must also recognize that becoming an effective educator is a continuous process as experience can be recognized for their innovative teaching methods (Smith, 2018). According to Pardo and Tellez (2015), teacher development comprises a protracted personal and professional process. This encourages ongoing self-reflection which strengthens teaching and learning potential. In this case, self-recognition and assessment of their teaching are observed, to improve classroom performance by producing materials suited to their students.

As affirmed by Erten (2015), educators play a significant part in the development and growth of a society. Therefore, it may be essential to understand the teacher candidates' ideology. By selecting teaching as a purposeful or willing option, their motivation can be maintained longer (Ekin et al., 2021). The correlation between career motivation and the educational beliefs of pre-service teachers has been shown in the study of Aycicek and Toraman (2020), which cites that pre-service teachers become aware of the responsibilities in the teaching profession through philosophical orientation. The results suggest that one should think about these responsibilities when deciding whether or not to stay in the profession. This is because making the wrong career choice can lead to long-term failure and dissatisfaction since it is hard for people to be effective and productive at work when there is no accountability and dedication. In contrast, the study of Kalaw (2018) on Motivational Factors and Teaching Philosophies of Education Students: Realizing the Vision of the Founder, Saint John Baptist de La Salle, discovered no statistically significant correlation between the pre-service teachers' reasons for entering the teaching profession and their pedagogical points of view.

Kim and Cho (2014) discovered that pre-service teachers' expectations of reality shock were directly correlated to external consequences but it was adversely linked to teacher efficiency. It was also found that pre-service teachers' feelings of efficiency and external motivation were significantly predictive of how adversely they would be surprised by the real world.

The findings from the study of SEAMEO INNOTECH Teacher Motivation Research Team (2020) note that there appeared to be only minor differences in the proportions of responses to the statement "I chose Education because it affords me the chance to serve others" based on the respondents' gender, teaching position, and geographic location among the nearly all (96%) teachers who chose Education as their major. Even though there were few respondents from rural locations, it is important to note that all six teachers from remote places chose to teach because of the chance to serve others. Moreover, more teachers strongly agreed that this chance to help others influenced their decision to become teachers. Contributing to society may continue to be a key motivator for people who choose to enter the teaching profession, as indicated by these data.

In their study about the motivation for choosing teacher education, Paulick et al. (2013) reveal that a teacher candidate's drive to succeed in the profession affects how they approach their teaching. They highlight the importance of mastery goals, which seize the individuals' desire to learn things professionally, and ability-approach goals, which involve the demonstration of superior teaching ability, as psychological factors that motivate pre-service teachers to pursue a career in teaching. Comparing these results with those from the past, however, reveals that teachers' mastery and ability-approach goals are linked to their well-being and job satisfaction (Retelsdorf et. al., 2010).

Ganal et al. (2015) investigate the concerns and difficulties encountered by 100 BEd and BSEd students during practical teaching. According to their findings, the most common adversities were related to homesickness, economic adjustment, students, classroom organization, language skills, instructional techniques, instructional materials and evaluation tools, test preparation and analysis, distinctive emotional responses, and overall adjustment to the cooperating school. Furthermore, it was concluded that student teaching both imparts theoretical knowledge and practical knowledge as pedagogy skills. In this sense, it was suggested that there is a need to arrange an orientation seminar on issues and conflict management to help students and teachers cope with challenges they may experience in the workplace or off-campus.

On the other hand, a study conducted by Tupas and Pendon (2016) on the educational philosophies of prospective teachers at West Visayas State University, Janiuay Campus, Philippines, found that progressivism was the most common educational philosophy across all demographics. Male and female, BEd and BEd, high GPA and low GPA students all agree that a teacher's job is to help students learn and that students need to take part in the learning process.

The perspectives of future educators on various approaches to education were also studied by Kumral (2014). The study found that a majority of future educators adhered to progressive, social reconstructionist, and existentialist philosophies. The results also indicated that essentialism and perennialism were more prevalent among pre-service educators majoring in Early Childhood Education, Elementary Education, and Social Science Education programs.

Magulod, Jr.'s (2017) research on the educational philosophies adhered to by Filipino pre-service teachers found that BSEd pre-service teachers placed themselves significantly and conservatively higher on the perennialism philosophy. It is because the students of BSEd programs with specialization are expected to have a deep and broad knowledge of linguistic and literary integration to effectively instruct their chosen subject. Aspiring teachers at Cagayan State University-Lasam also understand that teaching is about more than just passing on facts and information; they comprehend that it's also important to teach others about one's heritage and help them see the value of a well-written language. Uzuno (2016) studied and correlated the educational philosophy of 206 pre-service teachers and 32 in-service teachers. The findings found that the most often accepted educational philosophies for both groups were progressivism and existentialism, with essentialism ranking last. It was also inferred that the formation of teaching philosophy is closely tied to the influence of observation and actual teaching experiences. The personal teaching philosophy that a pre-service teacher has actively determined influences how they will arrange their classroom in the future.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

To address the research questions at hand, this study adopted a descriptive-correlational methodology. Melegrito and Mendoza (2016) define it as "a research strategy for describing and interpreting data." The current state of relationships, opinions, and processes or trends that are already in motion were also examined. In addition, it focuses primarily on the present, although it frequently considers past events and influences that have an impact on what is currently occurring.

This type of research applies to the study on hand, determining the relationship between the Fourth-year Education students' educational philosophy and their career motivation for choosing teaching as their profession.

Research Respondents

The respondents of the study were seventy-seven (77) pre-service teachers of Tayabas Western Academy. The sample size was determined from a population of ninety-six (96) fourth-year education students using Slovin's formula with a margin of error of 5%. The ratio and proportion method or pro-rata method was used to adjudicate the sample size, and the pre-service teachers in different educational programs were selected randomly using the fishbowl method.

The study was carried out using Google Forms as this was conducted during the peak of the COVID-19 pandemic, where face-to-face classes have been restricted to reduce the virus's devastating impact.

Research Instrument

This study used the adopted 25-item Philosophy of Education Survey of Sadker and Sadker (1997) and 8-item the Interest in Teaching Inventory of Kalaw (2018) to collect data on the specific research questions. The researchers utilized the mean and standard deviation from the answers to a Likert-scale question, where 4 means "strongly agree" and 1 means "strongly disagree." Moreover, for the dependent variable, a Likert scale was also used, 4 means 'highly motivated' and 1 means 'not motivated.'

Data Analysis

To better analyze and visualize the results from a reputable source, the following statistical tools were utilized:

The educational philosophies of pre-service teachers in various fields of specialization were described through a percentage distribution.

Using the mean and standard deviation, the researchers determined the level of pre-service teachers' perception of educational philosophy and career motivation for choosing teaching as a profession. Cronbach's alpha was used to evaluate the internal accuracy or validity of a set of scales for the educational philosophy and career motivation questionnaires.

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was utilized to identify the significant differences in the educational philosophies of pre-service teachers, such as essentialism, perennialism, progressivism, social reconstructionism, and existentialism.

The Pearson Product Moment of Correlation Coefficient or Pearson's r was used to assess how well two sets of continuous variables correspond with each other at the 0.05 and 0.01 levels of significance. This was done to find out if there was a meaningful correlation between the pre-service teachers' educational philosophy and their career motivation.

RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Table of Respondents' Educational Philosophies

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. Essentialism	2.94	0.78	Agree
2. Perennialism	2.86	0.80	Agree
3. Progressivism	3.15	0.85	Strongly Agree
4. Social Reconstructionism	2.69	0.82	Agree
5. Existentialism	3.01	0.80	Strongly Agree
Overall	2.92	0.81	Agree

Verbal Interpretation: 3.00 - 4.00 Strongly Agree; 2.00 - 2.99 Agree; 1.00 - 1.99 Disagree; 0.99 - 1.00 Strongly Disagree.

Table 1 shows the pre-service teachers' educational philosophies. As evident in the third item, which got the highest mean results, the dominant educational philosophy among the pre-service teachers in Tayabas Western Academy is progressivism. The pre-service teachers' favorable evaluation of progressivism embodies their view of learning by doing, in which they consider themselves as guides to assist their students. The result relates to the study by Tupas and Pendon (2016) on the prevailing educational philosophies among pre-service teachers at West Visayas State University, Janiway Campus, Philippines, which revealed that the pre-service teachers' educational philosophy is progressivism as a whole.

This is followed by the belief in existentialism (mean = 3.01, SD = 0.80), essentialism (mean = 2.94, SD = 0.78), perennialism (mean = 2.86, SD = 0.80), and social reconstructivism (mean = 2.69, SD = 0.82), respectively. Hence, the overall findings imply that the Fourth-year Education students at Tayabas Western Academy were found to be at an 'agree' level, which indicates that they are adaptable to particular educational philosophy and have tendencies to hold views or conceptions regarding their teaching approach.

Table 2. Percentage Distribution of the Respondents to the Different Educational Philosophies

Educational Program	Essentialism	Perennialism	Progressivism	Social Reconstructionism	Existentialism
BEEd	55.45%	52.73%	48.18%	44.55%	54.55%
BSEd Major in English	62.86%	45.71%	50%	38.57%	57.14%
BSEd Major in Filipino	57.78%	51.11%	51.11%	42.22%	50%
BSEd Major in General Science	48%	54%	44%	44%	50%
BSEd Major in Social Studies	52.5%	50%	52.5%	35%	55%
BSEd Major in Mathematics	40%	40%	56%	40%	60%

The table above shows the different educational philosophies of the Fourth-year Education students at Tayabas Western Academy. For BEEd, BSEd English, and BSEd Filipino courses, the majority of the respondents exemplify the philosophy of essentialism, which indicates their belief that instruction is teacher-centered and focuses on students' intellectual development rather than their social, emotional, or physical development. The research results can be interpreted in light of the fact that BEEd is a degree program with the goal of producing primary school teachers with interdisciplinary expertise. Therefore, having them achieve some level of literacy proficiency is essential if you want them to become experts in their field.

In the same manner, the pre-service teachers with specialization in English and Filipino considered language an essential competency to prepare students for further education, the workforce, and successful social and political involvement. According to Acquah et al. (2017), language is one of the subjects that can help schools teach students about the cultural and historical legacy of civilization by using the right skills, attitudes, and values, which can only be decided by the teacher.

However, the findings from these two courses, BSEd English and Filipino, are in contrast to that of Magulod, Jr. (2017), wherein he found out that the BSEd pre-service teachers of Cagayan State University- Lasam rated themselves moderately higher along the perennialism philosophy. This is because obtaining a BSEd with a specialization requires an in-depth understanding of how language and literature can be used to promote cultural enrichment and aesthetic appreciation. Cagayan State University-Lasam's future educators understand that their profession is tied to more than just the transmission of knowledge and facts.

Similarly, respondents from the BSEd General Science course define themselves as perennialist, which is concerned with the importance of topic mastery and the development of reasoning skills. In this context, the objective of education is to enhance the mind, which is the most essential aspect of human nature, and to educate students on how to utilize their minds following logical principles (Sonmez, 2014).

Finally, the dominating educational philosophy for the two remaining courses, BSEd Social Studies, and BSEd Mathematics is existentialism. This reflects their belief that learning is self-paced and self-directed because it fosters students' imagination and creativity more than copying and mimicking established lessons. The result is logical since these two specializations influence and pervade life at any age and in any circumstance.

Table 3. Respondents' Level of Motivation for Choosing Teaching as a Profession

Indicator	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. A major reason I considered becoming a teacher is job security.	2.68	0.90	Motivated
2. My family has strongly influenced my decision to become a teacher.	2.96	0.83	Motivated
3. The long summer vacation and extended breaks are essential to me when choosing to be a teacher.	2.35	0.87	Motivated
4. I have never really considered any other career besides teaching.	1.95	0.89	Less Motivated
5. A major reason for becoming a teacher is my desire to work with young people.	2.81	0.80	Motivated
6. I want to be a teacher because I would like to be of some value or significance to society.	2.97	0.92	Highly Motivated
7. The primary reason why I chose to become a teacher is because of the influence of a former elementary/high school teacher.	2.84	0.88	Motivated
8. The opportunity for self-improvement and personal development is the major reason I chose to be a teacher.	3.16	0.83	Highly Motivated
Overall	2.72	0.87	Motivated

Verbal Interpretation: 3.00 - 4.00 Highly Motivated; 2.00 - 2.99 Motivated; 1.00 - 1.99 Less Motivated; 0.99 - 1.00 Not Motivated.

Table 3 unveils the mean perception of the respondents on their motivation for choosing teaching as a profession. As examined carefully, the last indicator, "the opportunity for self-improvement and personal development," highlights the highest result (mean = 3.16, SD = 0.83) and implies that the respondents view teaching as a noble vocation requiring individuals who are informed, dependable, effective communicators, quick problem solvers, and innovators. As also manifested in the study of Pardo and Tellez (2015), teaching comprises a protracted personal and professional process that encourages

ongoing self-reflection to increase teaching and learning potentialities that benefit students' learning endeavors through contextualized resources. Thus, it may be concluded that the respondents' strong belief in selecting teaching as a career indicates that they recognize their potential as educators.

This is followed by "to be of some value or significance to society", which is somehow related to the findings of the SEAMEO INNOTECH Teacher Motivation Research Team (2020) that being able to contribute to society is one of the significant motivators for those who wish to enter the teaching profession. Notwithstanding, five indicators resulted in the same verbal interpretations: family influence (mean = 2.96, SD = 0.90), the influence of a former elementary or high school teacher (mean = 2.84, SD = 0.88), working with young people (mean = 2.81, SD = 0.80), job security (mean = 2.68, SD = 0.90), and long summer vacation and extended breaks (mean = 2.35, SD = 0.87).

Meanwhile, one indicator yielded 'less motivated' to the career motivation of never really considering any other career besides teaching. Being rated as the least-score one implies that some of the respondents have other alternative career options in mind before they pursue their teaching career. According to Ekin et al. (2021), it may be crucial to comprehend the idealism of prospective teachers. By picking education as their initial, deliberate, or willing option, their motivation can be maintained longer.

In general, these future educators have come to understand that honing their skills as educators and becoming proficient in a variety of approaches is the surest path to professional and personal growth. They recognize as well that educating the next generation of individuals is a challenging profession with its share of ups and downs, but they see their work as worthwhile because of the impact it will have on the world. As eloquently stated by Erten (2015) educators play a significant part in the development and growth of a society.

Table 4. Analysis of Variance in Educational Philosophies of the Respondents

Source of Variation		Summary of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p-value
Educational Philosophy	Between Groups	678.726	4	169.681	6.221	0.001*
	Within Groups	681.898	25	27.276		
	Total	1360.623	29			

Note. $N = 77$, *F value is significant at $p < 0.01$

It is depicted in Table 4 that the responses of all groups are significantly different as to the interpretation of the significance value presented. Respondents differ on educational philosophy, namely essentialism, perennialism, progressivism, social reconstructionism, and existentialism. Among the five educational philosophies, it is progressivism where the perceptions of the respondents differ greatly, and social reconstructionism where they differ the least. This indicates that the prevailing educational philosophy among Fourth-year Education students at Tayabas Western Academy is progressivism. It can be explained by the fact that the respondents envision themselves as future educators who will be able to effectively teach pupils from a wide range of backgrounds in a 21st-century classroom environment by emphasizing learner-centered, inquiry-based, interactive, interdisciplinary, contextualized, experiential, and collaborative teaching approaches. In contrast, social reconstructionism philosophy was rated as the least scored one, implying that the pre-service teachers do not have a clear belief that social reform is the fundamental aim of education, which demonstrates that they are not familiar with society and their surroundings. Thus, it is clear that pre-service teachers do not place a higher value on the role of education in resolving problems and issues in the real world.

Table 5. Correlation between the Educational Philosophy and the Career Motivation of the Respondents

Variable	r-value	p-value	Interpretation
Educational Philosophy/ Career Motivation	0.08	0.05	Significant

Note. $N = 77$, $\alpha < 0.05$

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When Table 5 is examined, it can be stated that there is a significant correlation between the pre-service teachers' educational philosophy and their career motivation for choosing teaching as a profession ($r = 0.08$), which suggests there is a pattern to identifying the educational philosophies of future teachers based on their reasons for entering the profession. For example, the "desire to work with young people" as a motivation to teach can be traced back to the progressivism philosophy. This suggests that students' career motivation for teaching promotes awareness of how they will decide on classroom practices that show their educational philosophy. The result relates to the study of Aycicek and Toraman (2020), where they emphasize that pre-service teachers become aware of the responsibilities in the teaching profession through philosophical orientation. The results suggest that one should think about these responsibilities when deciding whether or not to stay in the profession. This is because making the wrong career choice can lead to long-term failure and dissatisfaction since it is hard for people to be effective and productive at work when there is no accountability and dedication. However, the findings are in contrast to that of Kalaw (2018), who found no significant relationship between the pre-service teachers' motivations for choosing teaching as a profession and their teaching philosophies.

In general, the motivation for choosing teaching as a career cannot be taken for granted because it has a close relationship with the educational philosophy. Thus, educational philosophy and career motivation provide a clear perspective on its relevance in the field of education, especially by helping student teachers with their classroom instruction and also reducing their exposure to real shocks in the field, which results in a more sustainable teaching career.

CONCLUSION

The pre-service teachers of Tayabas Western Academy have diverse educational philosophies, which implies that they are adaptable to it and have a tendency to hold views or conceptions regarding their teaching approach. Likewise, their motivation to choose teaching as a profession showed that they are willing to embrace their chosen field of work even though teaching is not a simple job. As such, the following activities are proposed to be initiated by the College of Teacher Education: conduct of seminars/ webinars, workshops, consultations, and syllabus alignment about educational philosophy and career motivation orientation to strengthen the quality of education graduates.

Based on the results of the study, the following recommendations are summarized: The teacher education preparation program may well use philosophical and interest in teaching inventory to consider pre-service teachers' orientation. The school administrators may organize seminars/ webinars associated with the progressivist and existentialist philosophical orientations of the pre-service teachers to enhance their 21st-century teaching abilities. Among which are the following: the use of learner-centered approaches; cooperative projects and problem-solving activities; experiential learning; and planning of the lessons using an innovative design. The pre-service teachers' moderate commitment to essentialism, perennialism, and social reconstructionism may be clarified through seminar/ webinars and workshops along with classroom management and discipline, integration of values into teaching, time-tested teaching approaches, communicative approach, inquiry technique, simulation, and community-based learning. Educators may considerably promote teaching as a calling by strengthening pre-service teachers' desire or effort to serve others through consultations. To contextualize the identified key aspects, it is recommended that future studies on educational philosophy and career motivation may use in-depth qualitative research to give more information on the experiences and perspectives of teachers concerning their educational beliefs and motivations for choosing the profession.

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